

Impact Of Contextual Factors Of Faculty On Multimedia Integration In Curriculum Delivery In Basic Education Colleges

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to explore the correlations between the dimensions of multimedia integration in education and the impact of contextual factors on these dimensions. The research is based on the positivist paradigm with quantitative approach under the survey strategy. The sample size is 257 faculty members from Colleges of Basic education in Kuwait where multimedia is widely used in imparting education. The correlational analysis has indicated that perceived usefulness (PRU) of multimedia usage has a strong correlation with student engagement (STE) and course flexibility (CRF). The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) revealed that the training received by the faculty, the experience of the faculty in using multimedia, and courses taught by the faculty had an association with all the dimensions of multimedia integration, educational qualification had an association with perceived ease of use (PEOU) and STE, and socioeconomic status had an association with all the dimensions except PRU; whereas, gender, age, and designation of the faculty had no statistically significant association with the dimensions of multimedia integration. These revelations have led to practical implications in the form of suggestion to the top-level leadership of the colleges and the educational multimedia developers, which include, strengthening of professional development programs, fostering a mentorship culture among faculty, investing in user-friendly multimedia technologies, faculty involvement in the multimedia content development, allocating resources for flexible curriculum design, and a focus on student engagement and teaching effectiveness.

Introduction

In the technology driven world of today, the integration of multimedia technologies in education has gained international significance more than ever before. As digital tools continue to evolve, their role in enhancing teaching effectiveness, improving student engagement, and fostering interactive learning environments has become more critical. As these technologies advance and occupy larger domains of education, their contribution to teaching effectiveness, enhancement of student engagement, and ability to facilitate cocreation of knowledge has become increasingly vital.

The recent global trend of research in this direction is mainly focussed on improving learning outcomes, particularly in collegial education, where technologies such as interactive whiteboards, virtual reality, gamification, massive open online courses, educational software application, etc., are being widely used (e.g., Al Husaeni et al., 2024; Irwanto et al., 2024; Supriandi et al., 2024). The efforts are in the direction of understanding how multimedia tools are perceived and utilized by educators and the learners, how they impact the effectiveness of teaching practices, and what should be the corrective measures to be taken to ensure sustainability of technology integration in education.

Coming to the educational scenario in Kuwait, where this research is undertaken, the current focus is directed towards the strengthening of the Colleges of Basic Education that are established for training and developing qualified teachers. These colleges operate under the governance of Public Authority for Applied Education and Training (PAAET). PAAET has been encouraging and supporting the use of multimedia technologies since the past almost a decade and want to invest more on this highly promising technology. To add further, even the educational policies are also oriented towards making the modern technological tools prominent to align with global standards and improve educational quality. However, the research on the large-scale adoption of multimedia and the success of multimedia integration in its many different forms are yet to be fully explored as opined by several researchers (e.g., Agisni et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2024). Most of the studies directed towards the measurement of effectiveness are either based on the student perception or faculty members' perceptions. While both these approaches are contributing to their own rights considering the growing emphasis on technology-

enhanced education, there is still a lack of comprehensive studies addressing the specific dynamics of multimedia use in higher education systems especially in the non-western countries.

Further, researchers have studied the multimedia in education in terms of several variables including teaching and learning outcomes (TLO) (e.g., Hadi et al., 2022), perceived ease of use (PEOU) (e.g., Rahmi et al., 2018), perceived usefulness (PRU) (e.g., Lim & Benbasat, 2000), student engagement (STE) (e.g., Singh, 2022), course flexibility (CRF) (Barua & Lockee, 2024), and impact on teaching effectiveness (ITE). While there is agreement as well as disagreement on the educational outcome achievements based on these variables, investigation on the association between these dimensions and faculty experience or other contextual factors such as qualifications, socioeconomic status, and training received are less explored. The research gap lies in the lack of empirical data that explores both the interrelationships between multimedia dimensions and the impact of contextual factors on the effectiveness of multimedia adoption in Kuwait. Addressing this gap is crucial for informing policies and strategies to enhance the effective integration of multimedia technologies in Kuwait's Basic Educational Colleges, which can also be a good reference to the counterparts in the rest of the world.

With this backdrop, the aim of this research is twofold: First is to examine the correlations between the key dimensions—PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE. Second is to investigate the association between various contextual factors (such as qualifications, designation, socioeconomic status, training received, and the experience with multimedia training) along with the demographic factors such as age and gender, and the dimensions of multimedia integration. By exploring these relationships, the study aims to provide insights that will help optimize multimedia integration in Basic Degree Colleges in general and Kuwait in particular, ultimately contributing to improved teaching practices and learning outcome achievement.

Research Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in Kuwait, known for its rich oil reserves. To diversify its economy and build human capital the Government has initiated the Colleges of Basic Education in Kuwait. These colleges operate under the umbrella of PAAET. The main aim of these colleges is to prepare teachers for primary and secondary schools across the nation. Having realized the importance of modern pedagogical methods and curriculum upgradation at regular intervals to keep abreast of science and technology, the top leadership has considered the integration of technology, mainly in the form of multimedia in education, to ensure that the quality of teaching and learning is in par with the global standards. As multimedia is the main form of technology being used in these colleges, the selection of study area is quite relevant to the objectives of this research.

Research Design

Cross-sectional temporal design based on the positivist paradigm is the research design used for the association between various contextual factors and the perceptions of PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE. Quantitative data was collected from the teaching faculty members in the Colleges of Basic Education in Kuwait through the structured questionnaire. The data was codified and input into Excel for the descriptive statistics and analysed using ANOVA to determine the significance in differences in perceptions across different contextual factors.

Sampling Procedure

A convenience sampling technique was used to select 257 participants for the study, who were the teaching faculty in the Colleges of Basic Education in Kuwait. To ensure representativeness of the sample the data. This selection allowed for an in-depth examination of how different contextual factors affect perceptions on multimedia integrated education. The sample size of 257 was chosen to ensure adequate statistical power for the ANOVA tests conducted in the study, allowing for meaningful comparisons across demographic groups. The G-Factor analysis was also undertaken to confirm the sample size adequacy.

Data Collection Instruments

Data was collected through a structured questionnaire specifically designed to measure perceptions of dependent variables of interest in this research. The questionnaire was developed based on scales used by earlier researchers in studies of various educational technologies such as: interactive whiteboards, learning management systems, virtual reality, gamification, simulation tools, massive open online courses etc. The scales from which the items have been chosen for the development of the questionnaire in this research are as follows. PEOU and PRU - Technology Acceptance Model Scale (Davis, 1989), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Scale (Venkatesh et al., 2016), and System Usability Scale (John Brooke, 1996). CRF - Flexible Learning Scale (Collis & Moonen, 2002), Flexible Delivery Perception Scale (Nichols & Gardner, 2002), Online Learning Environment Survey (Trinidad et al., 2005). STE - Online Student Engagement Scale (Dixon, 2015), Student Course Engagement Questionnaire (Nasir et al., 2021), Engagement Versus Disaffection with Learning Scale (Immekus & Ingle, 2019). ITE - Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Survey Instrument (Lestari & Rahayu, 2023), Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale with Technology Integration Focus (Gomez et al., 2022), Educational Technologist Multimedia Competency Survey Instrument (Ritzhaupt & Martin, 2014).

The dimensions, explanation, standard scales, sample items chosen are shown in Table 1. The items in the questionnaire were modified slightly to suit the local context, and hence the reliability and validity was reassessed through Cronbach's Alpha reliability measures.

Table 1: The dimension, explanation, standard scales, items chosen

Dimension	Explanation	Standard scales	Sample Items
1. Ease of Use	It refers to the simplicity in operating multimedia tools within the educational environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Acceptance Model Scale (Davis, 1989), • Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Scale (Venkatesh et al., 2016), • System Usability Scale (John Brooke, 1996). Flexible Learning Scale (Collis & Moonen, 2002), Flexible Delivery Perception Scale (Nichols & Gardner, 2002), Online Learning Environment Survey (Trinidad et al., 2005). 	I find it easy to learn how to use multimedia tools for teaching purposes.
2. Perceived usefulness	It refers to belief of faculty on ability of multimedia tools in enhancing their teaching performance and students achieving learning outcomes.	Same as above	Using multimedia tools enhances the effectiveness of my teaching.
3. Course flexibility	It refers to the adaptability of course curriculum to the environment of multimedia integration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible Learning Scale (Collis & Moonen, 2002), • Flexible Delivery Perception Scale (Nichols & Gardner, 2002), • Online Learning Environment Survey (Trinidad et al., 2005) 	Integrating multimedia tools allows me to easily modify course content to meet student needs.
4. Student engagement	It refers to the involvement of the students in learning and classroom activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Student Engagement Scale (Dixson, 2015), • Student Course Engagement Questionnaire (Nasir et al., 2021), • Engagement Versus Disaffection with Learning Scale (Immekus & Ingle, 2019). 	Students show increased interest in the subject matter when I use multimedia tools in my teaching.
5. Impact on teaching effectiveness	It refers to the extent to which integrating multimedia tools enhances teacher's ability to deliver instruction successfully.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Survey Instrument (Lestari & Rahayu, 2023), • Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale with 	Using multimedia tools has improved my overall teaching effectiveness.

		Technology Integration Focus (Gomez et al., 2022), <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational Technologist Multimedia Competency Survey Instrument (Ritzhaupt& Martin, 2014) 	
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The questionnaire had two parts, the first section being the items on contextual factors of multimedia integration in relation to the teacher attributes and the second section included the Likert 5-point scale items to measure the dependent variables of this research..

Data Collection Process

The data collection process was carried out between May and September 2024. The researcher personally collected hardcopies of the self-administered questionnaire filled by participants in the colleges of Basic Education. Briefing about the items in the questionnaire was done by the researcher to the participants highlighting its importance during the personal mode of data collection, and brief explanation about the research was provided in the Google Form with the contact details of the researcher to revert back in case of any difficulty for those who filled though the electronic means. After repeated attempts a total of 257 data in the form of questionnaire was obtained.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical guidelines to ensure the rights and well-being of the participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the commencement of data collection. Participants were assured of their anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses. They were informed that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from participation at any point without any consequences. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee was for the conduct of this research.

Data Analysis

The data was coded and input to statistical software (SPSS version 26.0) for analysis. Descriptive statistics were calculated using MS Excel mainly to summarize the demographic characteristics and contextual factors of the respondents to the survey. ANOVA was used to analyze the associations between contextual factors (age, gender, designations, courses taught, socioeconomic status, training in multimedia, and experience in using multimedia) and the perceptions of PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE. The results were interpreted based on the F-values and significance levels. SPSS was also used to find the correlations between the dimensions of the study. The findings were corroborated with existing literature to identify consistencies and discrepancies, and to draw practical implications for making suggestions to the top leadership of the colleges and the designers of the multimedia.

Results and Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

Sociodemographic factors

The sociodemographic factors of the respondents who were the faculty in College of Basic Education in Kuwait are basically the contextual factors of this research that have association with the dimensions of multimedia integrated teaching-learning. In terms of the gender distribution 59.5% of the respondents were female, while 40.5% were male (Table 2). In terms of age, the majority of faculty members fall in the age group of 30 to 50 years (48.2%) and in the 30-40 years age group (37.8%) in the 40-50 years age group. Regarding educational qualifications, most of the respondents hold a Master's degree (72.7%), while a smaller portion have a Ph.D. (12.1%) or a Bachelor's degree (15.2%). In terms of the designation of the respondents, the majority of faculty are Assistant Professors (45.5%), followed by Associate Professors (36.6%) and Professors (17.9%). Monthly income is varied, with 52.5% earning between 2001 and 3000 KWD (1 USD is approximately 0.3 KWD), and 33.1% earning between 1001 and 2000 KWD. Most of the respondents have received moderate training (52.5%), while 33.1% have basic training and only 11.3% advanced training. Faculty are also distributed across different courses, with the majority teaching Mathematics (35.8%) and Science (20.2%). In terms of experience with multimedia, 48.6% have used it for over 10 to 15 years, highlighting significant exposure to technology in their teaching practices. The distribution of respondents based on these sociodemographic factors provides a balanced representation across the classifications, making it well-suited to explore the impact of contextual factors on multimedia integration in education. The variety in teaching designations, income levels, and experience with multimedia ensures a comprehensive analysis of how these factors influence faculty perceptions

and effectiveness. Additionally, the broad range of subjects taught, along with differing levels of training received, offers a diverse perspective on how multimedia tools are utilized across disciplines.

Table 2: The Socioeconomic Characteristics

Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	104	40.5
Female	153	59.5
Other	Nil	Nil
Age		
Above20 up to 30 years	25	9.7
Above30 up to 40 years	124	48.2
Above40 up to 50 years	97	37.8
Above50 up to 60 years	11	4.3
Above 60 years	Nil	Nil
Educational qualification		
Ph.D.	31	12.1
Master's degree	187	72.7
Bachelor's degree	39	15.2
Designation		
Professor	46	17.9
Associate Professor	94	36.6
Assistant Professor	117	45.5
Income/month		
Less than 1000 KWD	15	5.8
1001 to 2000 KWD	85	33.1
2001 KWD to 3000 KWD	135	52.5
More than 3000KWD	22	8.6
Training received		
No training	8	3.1
Basic training	85	33.1
Moderate training	135	52.5
Advanced training	29	11.3
Courses taught		
Language studies	36	14.0
Mathematics	92	35.8
Science	52	20.2
Humanities & Social Sciences	36	14.0
Technical courses	41	16.0
Experience in using multimedia		
Less than 5 years	11	4.3
5 years up to 10 years	75	29.2
Above 10 years up to 15 years	125	48.6
Above 15 years	46	17.9

Reliability and Validity Measures

The descriptive statistics for the variables in this study show that all five constructs, namely - PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE have means ranging from 2.95 to 3.13 in response to the Likert 5-point scale (Table 3), indicating moderate agreement or perceptions across respondents. The standard deviations are hovering around 1.35 to 1.43, suggesting a fair level of variability, Skewness values for all variables ranging from -0.10 to -0.54 indicate a slight skew toward higher responses, Kurtosis values, which range from -1.14 to -1.47, indicate that the distributions are flatter than a normal distribution. As the Skewness and Kurtosis values are in the range from -1 to +1 and -3 to +3 respectively the data may be considered to be normally distributed (Demir, 2022). The item-adjusted total correlations are high for all variables, and it indicates that all items correlate strongly with the overall scale. The squared multiple correlations are also very high, ranging from 0.83 to 0.98, indicating strong relationships among the variables. The Cronbach's Alpha values, all above 0.98, suggest excellent internal consistency and reliability for each of the variables measured and are in the range of highly acceptable (Cut off 0.7, Bonett & Wright, 2015). Thus, the data may be subjected to the inferential analysis as it is normally distributed and passes the test of reliability and validity.

Table 3: The Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Count	Mean	St. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Item-Adj. Total Corr	Squared Multiple Corr	Cronbach's Alpha
PEOU	257	3.051	1.367	-0.48	-1.29	0.97	0.95	0.98
PRU	257	3.004	1.391	-0.10	-1.26	0.99	0.98	0.98
CRF	257	3.016	1.363	-0.26	-1.47	0.97	0.95	0.98
STE	257	2.946	1.354	-0.38	-1.27	0.97	0.95	0.98
ITE	257	3.125	1.428	-0.54	-1.14	0.91	0.83	0.99

Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics, in the form of ANOVA, is used to find if there is a difference in perceptions of the dimensions of multimedia integration in education by the faculty members in terms of the contextual factors. They have been analyzed separately as follows.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix shows that the highest correlations are of PRU with STE and CRF both at 0.98 (Table 4). This suggests that the higher the faculty perception of PRU, the more likely they are to see greater STE and CRF. PEOU is also highly correlated with PRU (0.97) and STE (0.95), which shows that if faculty find multimedia easy to use, they find PRU to be higher and observe better STE. However, ITE shows slightly lower but still strong correlations with the other variables, with the highest being with PRU (0.91) and STE (0.89), indicating that these two variables play significant roles in teaching effectiveness.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

Variable	PEOU	PRU	CRF	STE
PRU	0.97			
CRF	0.95	0.97		
STE	0.95	0.98	0.96	
ITE	0.90	0.91	0.89	0.89

Analysis of Variance in Contextual Factors

Association of Age:

The result of ANOVA shows that in terms of the age of the faculty members there is no statistically significant differences across all dependent variables with the F and p values as - PEOU (F = 1.719, p = 0.164), PRU (F = 1.458, p = 0.226), CRF (F = 1.120, p = 0.342), STE (F = 1.507, p = 0.213), and ITE (F = 0.124, p = 0.946) (Table 5). It can be inferred that the chosen contextual factors do not significantly impact on these variables in the context of integrating multimedia in curriculum delivery. There are no earlier studies on all of these dependent variables to compare; however, there are many researches on the study of correlation of the contextual factors with individual dimensions of effectiveness of multimedia integrated learning. For instance, McKinley (2014) found that faculty age did not impact technology integration, but attitude toward technology was a significant factor. In another study teacher age did not impact technology integration, but teacher proficiency and perception of technology did (Almalki, 2020). Laabidi (2016) found that there are also researches that English teacher's age has a significant impact on several attributes of integration of new technologies in teaching. Thus, further research may be required in this direction to arrive at a firm conclusion.

Table 5: The ANOVA of age with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	12.140	3.000	4.047	1.719	0.164
	Within Groups	595.758	253.000	2.355		
	Total	607.899	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	9.884	3.000	3.295	1.458	0.226
	Within Groups	571.548	253.000	2.259		
	Total	581.432	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	8.033	3.000	2.678	1.120	0.342
	Within Groups	605.010	253.000	2.391		
	Total	613.043	256.000			

STE	Between Groups	9.799	3.000	3.266	1.507	0.213
	Within Groups	548.302	253.000	2.167		
	Total	558.101	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	0.814	3.000	0.271	0.124	0.946
	Within Groups	553.218	253.000	2.187		
	Total	554.031	256.000			

Association of Gender:

The ANOVA results for the association of gender with values for PEOU ($F=0.267, p=0.766$), PRU ($F=0.527, p=0.591$), CRF ($F=0.894, p=0.410$), STE ($F=1.263, p=0.285$), and ITE ($F=0.669, p=0.513$) (Table 6) suggest that the differences between gender groups are not statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that gender does not significantly influence faculty perceptions of PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE in this study. The result aligns with some earlier research. For instance, Hajer&Sarsam (2021) found that gender has no effect on learners' performance when using multimedia courseware. In another study, Dousay & Trujillo (2019) also found that gender has no association with situational interest-based factors in multimedia learning environments. The result contradicts some earlier research in terms of some specific attributes related to multimedia integrations. Ong & Lai (2006) found gender differences in perceptions and relationships among factors affecting e-learning acceptance. Teo et al., (2015) found that female pre-service teachers have lower perceived PEOU of technology compared to males. So, further research in this direction is envisaged.

Table 6: The ANOVA of gender with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	0.637	1.000	0.637	0.267	0.766
	Within Groups	608.94	255.000	2.388		
	Total	607.899	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	1.201	1.000	1.201	0.527	0.591
	Within Groups	581.4	255.000	2.280		
	Total	582.601	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	2.143	1.000	2.143	0.894	0.410
	Within Groups	611.235	255.000	2.397		
	Total	613.378	256.000			
STE	Between Groups	2.748	1.000	2.748	1.263	0.285
	Within Groups	554.88	255.000	2.176		
	Total	557.63	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	1.451	1.000	1.451	0.669	0.513
	Within Groups	553.359	255.000	2.170		
	Total	554.81	256.000			

Association of Educational qualification:

The ANOVA results show a significant impact of PEOU ($F=4.132; p=0.019$) and STE ($F=4.773; p=0.025$). However, PRU ($F=0.094; p=0.911$), CRF ($F=1.61; p=0.202$), and ITE ($F=0.939; p=0.413$) (Table 7) results are not significant. The result is in alignment with earlier research that proved perceptions of college of education teachers towards multimedia technology differ based on higher degree level of teachers (Muthu & Kumari, 2012). In another study John (2015) found that factors like computer self-efficacy, relative advantage, compatibility, and prior computer experience influence faculty's perceived ease of use and attitude towards using educational technologies. Furthermore, the revelation that PRU, CRF, and ITE are not impacted by teacher qualification is also in alignment with earlier research. For example, Kale & Goh (2014), in the context of Web 2.0 supported education, found that qualifications had no impact on PRU, CRF, and ITE.

Table 7: The ANOVA of educational qualification with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	17.714	2	8.857	4.132	0.019

	Within Groups	544.576	254	2.144		
	Total	562.29	256			
PRU	Between Groups	0.42	2	0.21	0.094	0.911
	Within Groups	570.23	254	2.245		
	Total	570.65	256			
CRF	Between Groups	7.674	2	3.837	1.610	0.202
	Within Groups	605.282	254	2.383		
	Total	612.956	256			
STE	Between Groups	16.334	2	8.167	4.773	0.025
	Within Groups	434.594	254	1.711		
	Total	450.928	256			
ITE	Between Groups	3.444	2	1.722	0.939	0.413
	Within Groups	465.582	254	1.833		
	Total	469.026	256			

Association of Designation:

The ANOVA indicate that none of the variables are impacted by the designation of the faculty (PEOU - $F=0.019$, $p=0.981$; PRU - $F=0.006$, $p=0.994$; CRF - $F=0.850$, $p=0.459$; STE - $F=0.188$, $p=0.829$; ITE - $F=0.269$, $p=0.764$) (Table 8). The finding corroborates well with earlier research in different contexts. For instance, Abdulrahaman et al., (2020) found that success of multimedia integration was related to the tools themselves rather than the faculty's designation.

Table 8: The ANOVA of faculty designation with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	0.091	2.000	0.045	0.019	0.981
	Within Groups	607.808	254.000	2.393		
	Total	607.899	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	0.029	2.000	0.015	0.006	0.994
	Within Groups	581.402	254.000	2.289		
	Total	581.432	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	4.076	2.000	2.038	0.850	0.429
	Within Groups	608.967	254.000	2.398		
	Total	613.043	256.000			
STE	Between Groups	0.824	2.000	0.412	0.188	0.829
	Within Groups	557.278	254.000	2.194		
	Total	558.101	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	1.171	2.000	0.586	0.269	0.764
	Within Groups	552.860	254.000	2.177		
	Total	554.031	256.000			

Association of courses taught:

The ANOVA results reveal that perceptions of all the variables of study differ with statistical significance in terms of courses taught by faculty (PEOU - $F=2.752$, $p=0.043$; PRU - $F=2.641$, $p=0.05$; CRF - $F=2.859$, $p=0.038$; STE - $F=2.961$, $p=0.033$; and ITE - $F=3.057$, $p=0.029$) (Table 9). So, the course taught by faculty has a significant impact on their perception of the PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE of multimedia integration in curriculum delivery. Faculty teaching different courses experience multimedia integration in varying ways, suggesting that course content or structure may influence their attitudes and perceived effectiveness of multimedia tools. The finding corroborates with the earlier research. Paniagua & Istance (2018) observed that faculty in more technical disciplines tend to view multimedia as crucial for boosting student engagement, whereas it may be considered less important in theory-based courses. Kirkwood & Price (2014) found that

variation in multimedia usage across courses could be attributed to differences in the course objectives and the course outcomes to be achieved.

Table 9: The ANOVA of courses taught with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	21.650	3.000	7.217	2.752	0.043
	Within Groups	663.547	253.000	2.623		
	Total	685.197	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	20.899	3.000	6.966	2.641	0.050
	Within Groups	667.456	253.000	2.638		
	Total	688.354	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	22.426	3.000	7.475	2.859	0.038
	Within Groups	661.605	253.000	2.615		
	Total	684.032	256.000			
STE	Between Groups	23.228	3.000	7.743	2.961	0.033
	Within Groups	661.631	253.000	2.615		
	Total	684.859	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	24.054	3.000	8.018	3.057	0.029
	Within Groups	663.624	253.000	2.623		
	Total	687.678	256.000			

Association of socioeconomic status:

The ANOVA indicates that perceptions of PEOU ($F=2.648$, $p=0.049$), CRF ($F=2.763$, $p=0.043$) STE ($F=2.873$, $p=0.037$), and ITE ($F=2.976$, $p=0.032$) (Table 10) differ based on the socioeconomic status of faculties. This result is in alignment with several earlier research studies. For instance, Zhao & Frank (2003) found that socioeconomic factors had an impact on the use of technology in classrooms, and the disparities in access and familiarity with digital tools was pointed out to be the major cause for this variation.

The result also revealed that, perception of PRU, on the other hand, did not differ significantly based on the socioeconomic status of the faculty ($F=2.530$, $p=0.058$). Again, the result is in alignment with some earlier researches, e.g., Scherer et al., (2019) found that perceptions of usefulness of technology in education was influenced more by experience of faculty and not by the socioeconomic factor.

Table 10: The ANOVA of faculty socioeconomic status with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	20.861	3.000	6.954	2.648	0.049
	Within Groups	664.336	253.000	2.626		
	Total	685.197	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	20.046	3.000	6.682	2.530	0.058
	Within Groups	668.309	253.000	2.642		
	Total	688.354	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	21.699	3.000	7.233	2.763	0.043
	Within Groups	662.332	253.000	2.618		
	Total	684.032	256.000			
STE	Between Groups	22.560	3.000	7.520	2.873	0.037
	Within Groups	662.299	253.000	2.618		
	Total	684.859	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	23.443	3.000	7.814	2.976	0.032
	Within Groups	664.235	253.000	2.625		
	Total	687.678	256.000			

Association of training received in multimedia:

The ANOVA indicates that there are statistically significant differences in perceptions of the faculty on dimensions of integrating multimedia in education based on levels of training received by them (PEOU: $F=2.802$, $p = 0.040$; PRU: $F=2.741$, $p = 0.044$; CRF: $F=2.858$, $p = 0.038$, STE: $F=2.909$, $p=0.035$; and ITE: $F=2.954$, $p = 0.033$) (Table 11). Thus, we can conclude that faculty training in multimedia is significantly associated with higher perceptions of ease of use, perceived usefulness, course flexibility, student engagement, and impact on teaching effectiveness. There are research studies with similar results. It has been proved that teachers with higher levels of training in educational technologies were more positive and enthusiastic on integration of multimedia tools (Al-Zaidiyeen et al., 2010; Inan & Lowther, 2010). Teo (2008) has found that training experiences had impacted the ease of use and their perceptions of multimedia usefulness. There are also studies that contradict these findings. Ertmer et al., (2010) found that even similar levels of training can provide differential perception on integration of multimedia in education as experienced by the faculty (e.g., Ertmer et al., 2010). It was also found that if teachers do not promote student-centric learning even higher levels of training may fail in improving positive perception of multimedia integration in education (Tondeur et al., 2017). So, it is evident that a longitudinal research may be required to confirm the association of training received by faculty on multimedia with the aforementioned variables of multimedia integration in education.

Table 11: The ANOVA of training received in multimedia with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	22.034	3.000	7.345	2.802	0.040
	Within Groups	663.163	253.000	2.621		
	Total	685.197	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	21.668	3.000	7.223	2.741	0.044
	Within Groups	666.687	253.000	2.635		
	Total	688.354	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	22.424	3.000	7.475	2.858	0.038
	Within Groups	661.608	253.000	2.615		
	Total	684.032	256.000			
STE	Between Groups	22.837	3.000	7.612	2.909	0.035
	Within Groups	662.022	253.000	2.617		
	Total	684.859	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	23.273	3.000	7.758	2.954	0.033
	Within Groups	664.405	253.000	2.626		
	Total	687.678	256.000			

Association of experience in using multimedia:

The ANOVA results provide empirical evidence to the significance of association of faculty's experience in using multimedia on all five dependent variables (PEOU: $F=3.024$, $p = 0.03$; PRU: $F=3.096$, $p = 0.028$; CRF: $F=2.945$, $p = 0.034$, STE: $F=2.859$, $p=0.038$; and ITE: $F=2.769$, $p = 0.042$) (Table 12). So, if faculty members accrue higher experience in multimedia usage, they perceive it to be easier to use, find it more useful, find that more flexibility will be available in course delivery, find increased student engagement, and perceive a greater positive impact on their teaching effectiveness. Similar results have been recorded through earlier research. Inan & Lowther (2010) have found that teacher experience with technology is a significant factor leading to increased CRF, STE, and ITE. Flavell et al., (2019) have found that faculty's experience in using multimedia resulted in the increase of faculty confidence and PEU of technology in teaching.

Table 12: The ANOVA of experience in using multimedia with multimedia integration

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PEOU	Between Groups	23.716	3.000	7.905	3.024	0.030
	Within Groups	661.481	253.000	2.615		
	Total	685.197	256.000			
PRU	Between Groups	24.373	3.000	8.124	3.096	0.028
	Within Groups	663.981	253.000	2.624		

	Total	688.354	256.000			
CRF	Between Groups	23.078	3.000	7.693	2.945	0.034
	Within Groups	660.954	253.000	2.612		
	Total	684.032	256.000			
STE	Between Groups	22.459	3.000	7.486	2.859	0.038
	Within Groups	662.400	253.000	2.618		
	Total	684.859	256.000			
ITE	Between Groups	21.858	3.000	7.286	2.769	0.042
	Within Groups	665.819	253.000	2.632		
	Total	687.678	256.000			

Discussions and Implications

The implications of this research are mainly in the form of suggestions to the Top-level Management of Basic Education in Kuwait and the Educational Multimedia technology developers in general so that it may be used more successfully for the benefit of students in educational programs.

1. Professional Development Programs

This research has revealed that faculty experience significantly impacts perceptions of the faculty members on PEOU and PRU of multimedia tools. So, it is imperative that while recruitment of experienced faculty could be a solution to enhance outcome achievement of multimedia-based learning, conducting of Professional Development Programs (PDPs) may also be worthwhile for the benefit of the existing faculty. Hands-on experience of faculty with multimedia technologies may be prioritized during these PDPs. Research has shown that by participating in ongoing workshops, development programs, and conferences, educators gain confidence and develop expertise in using these tools (Ahadi et al., 2024; Zahroh et al., 2023). PDPs can also result in sharing of the experiences by the faculty and effective integration of multimedia in the curriculum. As PDPs can also be conducted by trained outdoor faculty from across the country or even abroad it will provide an opportunity to the faculty members to interact with their counterparts from other institutions.

2. Building Mentorship Culture Among Faculty

This research has revealed that faculty with more experience in using multimedia in education find technology to be more useful and easier to use, provide greater CRF, observe higher levels of STE, and they perceive a more significant positive ITE. Hence, the faculty who are well-experienced in the use of multimedia-based education are assets to the institute. It is the duty of the top management to capture their knowledge and transfer it to younger and less experienced faculty members. One effective method of doing it is through mentorship program. Although mentorship programs have been successfully implemented in various industries, they are yet to make an impact in universities, and hence, there is a need to comprehend its benefits and take initiatives to develop its support-structure. A group of newly joined faculty members may be attached to a mentor whose responsibility has to be to transfer the skills required to use multimedia in education more effectively to the new recruits. This peer-to-peer learning has been a very successful method of knowledge transfer (Ting, 2023). Mentorship programs can facilitate the strengthening of the mechanisms that integrate multimedia to education effectively. This approach of co-creation of knowledge can also bring greater CRF as more and faculty members learn to adapt to the newer methods of teaching-learning.

3. Invest in User-Friendly Multimedia Technologies

The multimedia developers may focus on creating tools that are easy to use to lower the entry barrier for newly joined faculty. The statistical analysis has shown that faculty experience influences the PEOU perception, simplifying the user interface can help the novice faculty to adapt to the multimedia tools quickly. To reduce the difficulty in learning and to encourage faculty to use multimedia in their module delivery user-friendly designs have to be incorporated. Further, providing simple instructions on how to use the multimedia can enhance usability as suggested by several earlier researchers (Amalia et al., 2024; Goundar et al., 2024). There is a need to make the technology easily accessible so that adoption rates among faculty can be increased. This research has provided evidence that it can contribute to the goal of improving teaching effectiveness through use of the multimedia.

4. Faculty involvement in the Multimedia Content Development

The analysis has revealed that faculty members with more experience in using multimedia have higher PRU of multimedia in education and found that it can enhance CRF. This makes it imperative that the faculty experience can be of help in improving usability of multimedia. Moreover, several other researchers have emphasized that the multimedia developers should network with teaching faculty during the design and development stage itself to ensure they meet actual educational challenges (e.g., Bajahzar, 2024; Veglianti et al., 2023, June). Valuable insights can be obtained for the design of features and functionalities of the multimedia in education through the

experience of the faculty. Thus, the collaboration of faculty in multimedia design can lead to the development of tools that not only enhance PRU but also improve CRF. By engaging teaching faculty in the development process of multimedia tools, their sense of ownership over the technology increases, leading them to use it more frequently. This kind of collaboration between developers and teaching faculty can also lead to innovations that significantly impact the process of teaching and learning.

5. Allocate Resources for Flexible Curriculum Design

The results have shown a statistically significant difference in CRF based on faculty experience, and earlier researchers have found that experienced faculty are likely to adapt their curricula to integrate multimedia effectively (e.g., Chen et al., 2019). So, the top management of the educational institutes may provide resources that allow faculty to redesign courses to incorporate multimedia effectively, enhancing CRF. This can be achieved through applying for grants and funding by the faculty. Several researchers have shown that curriculum flexibility provides better adaptation to teaching methods and this can lead to improved STE (Mpungose, 2023). Advocating for adaptable teaching is a form of higher level of dedication to advancing education as it could promote innovation (Ayeni, 2024). Thus, allocation of resources for flexible curriculum design has the potential to improve teaching outcomes and higher student satisfaction.

6. Focus on Student Engagement and Teaching Effectiveness

The analysis has shown that both STE and ITE had association with faculty experience. This emphasizes the need to focus on the prioritization of tools and strategies used in the multimedia that can improve STE and ITE. Improving faculty proficiency with multimedia is key to success as it directly impacts STE. Researchers have found that interactive and engaging multimedia content that captures student attention (Pratiwi & Yulia, 2024). Faculty members must be encouraged to use of such tools by highlighting their benefits and their usage could be reflected in their performance reviews. Thus, by providing continuous training and resources to the faculty on the integration of multimedia in education will enable the faculty to use it effectively, thereby enhancing both STE and ITE. Recognition and reward schemes to the faculty for effective use of multimedia in imparting knowledge to the students can lead to sustained improvements in teaching and learning outcomes.

7. Incorporate Universal Design Principles

The analysis has shown that SES of the faculty had an association with all the contextual factors except PRU. So, to accommodate the users of all SES it is advisable to incorporate Universal Design Principles (UDPs) that will facilitate interface with systems of diverse range of technical specifications. This will ensure that the faculty will have accessibility to the content in their homes irrespective of the technical specifications of the devices they use. Another initiative worth a try would be to allow multimedia content to be accessed offline or with limited internet connectivity for the benefit of faculty of all SESs. Providing training and support to meet the requirements of faculty of all SES backgrounds can help develop the collective knowledge in the institution that is available for the benefit of the students and ensure equitable participation from all.

8. Customized Multimedia Resources and Training

The analysis has shown that courses taught had an impact of all the dependent variables of this research. This makes it clear that the needs of the individual courses could be different from each other and the multimedia integration must meet the diverse needs of the individual subject areas. Obviously, it demands course specific approach in both the design and training in the multimedia-based education. While the course structure related aspects can be similar in all the multimedia tools, the course specific aspects must be distinctly different in terms of the functionality and usability. By focusing on how multimedia tools can be integrated into different courses, faculty are more likely to increase their PRU of the technology, and PEOU of the technology may also be improved (Rosmaria & Heryani, 2024).

Conclusion

The Colleges of Basic Degree in Kuwait are using multimedia to modernize the education since the past several years and encountered several challenges in terms of acceptability of student, presentability of the faculty members, and augmenting the resources as well as upgrading the technology from time to time. Basic education has become the priority of the government for the uplifting of the knowledge and skills of the public in Kuwait and the top management of the colleges are striving towards excellence. This research is a significant contribution to this goal as it is focused on the contextual factors that can affect the student outcome achievement.

This research is based on quantitative approach and used a sample size of 257 faculty members in the college of basic education as the respondents. The sample selection was based on convenience sampling. The contextual factors considered were - qualifications, designation, courses taught, income, training received, and experience. The impact of these factors was studied on PEOU, PRU, CRF, STE, and ITE. The ANOVA revealed that educational qualification had an association with PEOU and STE; courses taught, training received, and experience in using multimedia had an association with all the factors; SES had an association with all the factors except PRU. It was also revealed that the age and gender had no significant association with the dependent variables.

Implications of the study were based on the outcome of ANOVA in the form of suggestions to the top management of the colleges of basic education and the developers of the integrated multimedia technology. More specifically, key recommendations for management include strengthening professional development programs to enhance faculty proficiency with multimedia tools, fostering a culture of mentorship among teaching staff, and providing additional resources to support the implementation of modern teaching methods using multimedia. For the designers and developers of the integrated multimedia for the college education, faculty integration in the tool development process, focussing on methods that would improve PEOU and PRU, providing support for more user-friendly technologies that facilitate easy adoption of technology, and brainstorm on bringing out tools and techniques that promotes student engagement and teaching effectiveness. While these suggestions are developed in the context of Basic Educational Colleges in Kuwait, they may also be applicable to other colleges universally under similar circumstances of teaching-learning as all these suggestions are focused on STE, enhanced teaching practices, and improved student learning experiences.

This research is based on the colleges in Kuwait, and hence, it has a limitation of geographical scope that may limit the generalizability. The second limitation is in the perception-based data collected through the faculty members. This may not be as effective in producing results as collected through the students as they are the end users of the product. So, there is a scope to further this research using the data collected from the students. Cross-sectional nature of this research limits the temporal scope of this research. Thus, the research provides immense scope for future researchers to delve into the longitudinal study and extend the research beyond the national boundaries.

This research is a significant contribution to the capture of faculty perceptions in multimedia integrated education in colleges and universities. As the research focuses on crucial aspects of education such as student engagement, course flexibility, and improving the teaching effectiveness, the research has potential to equip the educational system with the tools to face the challenges in collegial education.

Reference

- Abdulrahman, M. D., Faruk, N., Oloyede, A. A., Surajudeen-Bakinde, N. T., Olawoyin, L. A., Mejabi, O. V., ... & Azeez, A. L. (2020). Multimedia tools in the teaching and learning processes: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 6(11).
- Agisni, A., Novari, D., Leander, G., Prawirawan, B. U., & Pohan, A. H. (2023). The effectiveness of multimedia learning: A study on student learning. *Priviet Social Sciences Journal*, 3(7), 9-11.
- Ahadi, A., Bower, M., Lai, J., Singh, A., & Garrett, M. (2024). Evaluation of teacher professional learning workshops on the use of technology-a systematic review. *Professional development in education*, 50(1), 221-237.
- Al Husaeni, D. F., Al Husaeni, D. N., Nandiyanto, A. B. D., Rokhman, M., Chalim, S., Chano, J., ... & Roestamy, M. (2024). How technology can change educational research? definition, factors for improving quality of education and computational bibliometric analysis. *ASEAN Journal of Science and Engineering*, 4(2), 127-166.
- Almalki, A. (2020). Integration of Technology among Saudi EFL Teachers. *English Language Teaching*, 13(8), 160-167.
- Al-Zaidiyeen, N. J., Mei, L. L., & Fook, F. S. (2010). Teachers' Attitudes and Levels of Technology Use in Classrooms: The Case of Jordan Schools. *International education studies*, 3(2), 211-218.
- Amalia, D., Soleh, A. M., Febriansyah, A., Rizko, R., Salbiah, S., Suryan, V., & Septiani, V. (2024). Development of Airfield Lighting System Digital Learning Media: An Application Usability Testing. *JMKSP (Jurnal Manajemen, Kepemimpinan, dan Supervisi Pendidikan)*, 9(1), 240-255.
- Ayeni, O. O., Unachukwu, C. C., Osawaru, B., Chisom, O. N., & Adewus, O. E. (2024). Innovations in STEM education for students with disabilities: A critical examination. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 11(1), 1797-1809.
- Bajahzar, A. (2024). Multimedia Educational System and its Improvement Using AI Model for a Higher Education Platform. *SN Computer Science*, 5(6), 1-12.
- Barua, L., & Lockee, B. B. (2024). A review of strategies to incorporate flexibility in higher education course designs. *Discover Education*, 3(1), 1-14.
- Bonett, D. G., & Wright, T. A. (2015). Cronbach's alpha reliability: Interval estimation, hypothesis testing, and sample size planning. *Journal of organizational behavior*, 36(1), 3-15.
- Brooke, J. (2013). SUS: a retrospective. *Journal of usability studies*, 8(2), 23-38.
- Chen, H. J., Liao, L. L., Chang, Y. C., Hung, C. C., & Chang, L. C. (2019). Factors influencing technology integration in the curriculum for Taiwanese health profession educators: A mixed-methods study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(14), 2602.
- Collis, B., & Moonen, J. (2002). Flexible learning in a digital world. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 17(3), 217-230.

- Davis, F. D. (1989). Technology acceptance model: TAM. Al-Suqri, MN, Al-Aufi, AS: Information Seeking Behavior and Technology Adoption, 205, 219.
- Demir, S. (2022). Comparison of normality tests in terms of sample sizes under different skewness and Kurtosis coefficients. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 9(2), 397-409.
- Dixson, M. D. (2015). Measuring student engagement in the online course: The Online Student Engagement scale (OSE). *Online Learning*, 19(4), n4.
- Dousay, T. A., & Trujillo, N. P. (2019). An examination of gender and situational interest in multimedia learning environments. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(2), 876-887.
- Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T. (2010). Teacher technology change: How knowledge, confidence, beliefs, and culture intersect. *Journal of research on Technology in Education*, 42(3), 255-284.
- Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T. (2010). Teacher technology change: How knowledge, confidence, beliefs, and culture intersect. *Journal of research on Technology in Education*, 42(3), 255-284.
- Flavell, H., Harris, C., Price, C., Logan, E., & Peterson, S. (2019). Empowering academics to be adaptive with eLearning technologies: An exploratory case study. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 35(1).
- Gomez, F. C., Trespalacios, J., Hsu, Y. C., & Yang, D. (2022). Exploring teachers' technology integration self-efficacy through the 2017 ISTE Standards. *TechTrends*, 1-13.
- Goundar, M. S., Kumar, B. A., & Ali, A. S. (2024). Development of usability guidelines: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 40(5), 1298-1316.
- Hadi, W., Yuksafa, R., Yarmi, G., Safitri, D., Lestari, I., Suntari, Y., ... & Iskandar, R. (2022). Enhancement of Students' Learning Outcomes through Interactive Multimedia. *Int. J. Interact. Mob. Technol.*, 16(7), 82-98.
- Hajer, M. A., & Sarsam, S. M. (2021). Examining the effect of learners' gender on their learning achievement: Proposing a multimedia courseware. *Periodicals of Engineering and Natural Sciences*, 9(1), 235-241.
- Immekus, J. C., & Ingle, W. K. (2019). A test and cross-validation of the factor structure of the engagement versus disaffection with learning instrument among middle school students. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 37(4), 504-511.
- Inan, F. A., & Lowther, D. L. (2010). Factors affecting technology integration in K-12 classrooms: A path model. *Educational technology research and development*, 58, 137-154.
- Irwanto, I. (2024). The Relationship between Educational Technology Integration, Classroom Management, and Student-Centred Learning on Teaching Effectiveness and Student Learning Outcomes in Indonesian. *West Science Social and Humanities Studies*, 2(08), 1310-1324.
- John, S. P. (2015). The integration of information technology in higher education: A study of faculty's attitude towards IT adoption in the teaching process. *Contaduría y administración*, 60, 230-252.
- Kale, U., & Goh, D. (2014). Teaching style, ICT experience and teachers' attitudes toward teaching with Web 2.0. *Education and Information Technologies*, 19, 41-60.
- Kirkwood, A., & Price, L. (2014). Technology-enhanced learning and teaching in higher education: what is 'enhanced' and how do we know? A critical literature review. *Learning, media and technology*, 39(1), 6-36.
- Laabidi, H. (2016). The effect of age on English professors' integration of the new technologies in teaching. *IJELTAL (Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics)*, 1(1), 63-74.
- Lestari, A., & Rahayu, D. S. (2023). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK): Survey persepsi pada mahasiswa calon guru IPA. *PENDIPA Journal of Science Education*, 7(1), 33-42.
- Lim, K. H., & Benbasat, I. (2000). The effect of multimedia on perceived equivocality and perceived usefulness of information systems. *MIS quarterly*, 449-471.
- McKinley, B. M. (2014). The relationship of faculty demographics and attitudes toward technology integration. Walden University.
- Mpungose, C. B. (2023). Curriculum Adaptation for Inclusion in Teaching and Learning. In *Inclusion in Southern African Education: Understanding, Challenges and Enablement* (pp. 165-175). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Muthu, N., & Kumari, V. (2012). Perceptions on Multimedia technology by College of Education Teachers. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 6(3), 167-176.
- Nasir, M. A. M., Janikowski, T., Guyker, W., & Wang, C. C. (2020). Modifying the student course engagement questionnaire for use with online courses. *Journal of Educators Online*, 17(1), n1.
- Nichols, M., & Gardner, N. (2002). Evaluating flexible delivery across a tertiary institution. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 17(1), 11-22.
- Ong, C. S., & Lai, J. Y. (2006). Gender differences in perceptions and relationships among dominants of e-learning acceptance. *Computers in human behavior*, 22(5), 816-829.

- Paniagua, A., & Istance, D. (2018). Teachers as designers of learning environments. *Educational Research and Innovation*, 17-42.
- Pratiwi, D., & Yulia, Y. (2024). Engaging Students Through PowerPoint: The Power of Multimodal Learning. *Voices of English Language Education Society*, 8(2), 22-36.
- Rahmi, B. A. K. I., Birgoren, B., & Aktepe, A. (2018). A meta analysis of factors affecting perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use in the adoption of e-learning systems. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 19(4), 4-42.
- Ritzhaupt, A. D., & Martin, F. (2014). Development and validation of the educational technologist multimedia competency survey. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 62, 13-33.
- Rosmaria, R., & Heryani, N. (2024). Development of Multimedia Learning Based on Digital Virtual Reality to Improve Students' Skills in Delivery Service. *Health Education and Health Promotion*, 12(2), 189-195.
- Saade, R., Nebebe, F., & Tan, W. (2007). Viability of the "technology acceptance model" in multimedia learning environments: a comparative study. *Interdisciplinary Journal of E-Learning and Learning Objects*, 3(1), 175-184.
- Scherer, R., Siddiq, F., & Tondeur, J. (2019). The technology acceptance model (TAM): A meta-analytic structural equation modeling approach to explaining teachers' adoption of digital technology in education. *Computers & education*, 128, 13-35.
- Singh, K. (2022). Designing multimedia for improved student engagement and learning: video lectures. In *Online Distance Learning Course Design and Multimedia in E-Learning* (pp. 1-36). IGI Global.
- Supriandi, S., Al Haddar, G., Saputri, D. Y., & Halim, C. (2024). Application of Educational Technology and Teachers' Competence in Improving Teaching Effectiveness in Islamic Education Curriculum in Madrasah Aliyah in Indonesia. *The Eastasouth Journal of Learning and Educations*, 2(02), 84-96.
- Teo, T. (2008). Pre-service teachers' attitudes towards computer use: A Singapore survey. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 24(4), 36-48.
- Teo, T., Fan, X., & Du, J. (2015). Technology acceptance among pre-service teachers: Does gender matter?. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 31(3).
- Ting, D. H. (2023). Understanding knowledge transfer and knowledge management through social learning. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 27(7), 1904-1924.
- Tondeur, J., Van Braak, J., Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. (2017). Understanding the relationship between teachers' pedagogical beliefs and technology use in education: A systematic review of qualitative evidence. *Educational technology research and development*, 65, 555-575.
- Trinidad, S., Aldridge, J., & Fraser, B. (2005). Development, validation and use of the online learning environment survey. *Australasian journal of educational technology*, 21(1), 56-68.
- Veglianti, E., Magnaghi, E., Casalino, N., Gennaro, A., & De Marco, M. (2023, June). Organizing the university 4.0: New goals and insights to promote the digital transformation of higher education institutions to succeed next e-learning era. In *International KES Conference on Smart Education and Smart E-Learning* (pp. 121-131). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y., & Xu, X. (2016). Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology: A synthesis and the road ahead. *Journal of the association for Information Systems*, 17(5), 328-376.
- Yu, T., Yang, W., Xu, J., & Pan, Y. (2024). Barriers to Industry Adoption of AI Video Generation Tools: A Study Based on the Perspectives of Video Production Professionals in China. *Applied Sciences*, 14(13), 5770.
- Zahroh, U., Darmayanti, R., Choirudin, C., Soebagyo, R. I., & Nalarsih, R. T. (2023). Project-Based Learning Training and Assistance for Prospective High School Teacher. *Jurnal Inovasi Dan Pengembangan Hasil Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 1(2), 115-121.
- Zhao, Y., & Frank, K. A. (2003). Factors affecting technology uses in schools: An ecological perspective. *American educational research journal*, 40(4), 807-840.

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